

MMLN: An R Package for Mixed-Effects Multinomial Logistic-Normal Regression and Model Diagnostics

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Abstract

Multinomial outcomes arise in numerous fields---from sports and species counts to genomics---yet existing software often focuses on simpler fixed-effects or purely multinomial (logistic) frameworks. The **MMLN** package introduces a suite of functions to fit more complex multinomial logistic-normal regression models, including incorporation of random effects, and evaluate the fit of all multinomial regression models using the squared Mahalanobis distance residuals [6].

The `MMLN()` function fits mixed-effects multinomial logistic-normal models via MCMC sampling, while the `MDres()` function computes the squared Mahalanobis distance residuals to comprehensively evaluate model adequacy. Users can visualize or formally test these using quantile-quantile plots and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests. We describe the design and usage of the functions provided in the **MMLN** package and demonstrate the package's capabilities for modeling multinomial data by integrating flexible modeling tools, summaries, visualization, and robust diagnostics.

Key Words: multinomial regression, mixed effects models, residuals, diagnostics

1. Introduction

Multinomial logistic-normal (MLN) models extend the classical multinomial framework by embedding the probability vectors of the multinomial data in a latent Gaussian space, more robustly accounting for overdispersion among categories than traditional multinomial logit or hierarchical multinomial-Dirichlet models. Bayesian hierarchical models are powerful tools for fitting both fixed-effect and mixed-effect MLN models used for capturing overall and group-level covariance structures among the multinomial categories. Posterior predictive checks provide essential diagnostics for assessing model adequacy but have historically been difficult to derive or unintuitive for multinomial models of any type. Squared Mahalanobis residuals calculated using samples from predictive distributions have been developed to address this gap [6].

The **MMLN** package implements both fixed-effects and mixed-effects MLN models using Gibbs sampling with flexible Metropolis-Hastings updates, accompanied by tools for residual analysis in **R**. The specific MLN functions add to the lexicon of established multinomial regression models, while the `MDres()` function is simple to use for assessing model fits under any multinomial regression framework, from models as complex as MLN to as simple as basic multinomial logit.

2. Multinomial Logistic-Normal Models and Diagnostics

Define the general form for a nominal outcome regression model:

$$y_i \sim \mathcal{M}_J(n_i, \pi_i)$$

where \mathcal{M}_J represents the multinomial distribution with J categories, exposure $n_i > 1$, and probability vector π_i .

The commonly fit model to these data, the multinomial logistic, struggles to account for overdispersion and cannot account for positive correlations between the outcome counts of the different categories. The multinomial Dirichlet model has been shown as one option for accounting for overdispersion [7]. However, the multinomial logistic-normal is a more flexible alternative, which does a better job of accounting for positive correlations between categories [1].

Multinomial logistic-normal models arise from modeling the probability vector using the inverse additive logistic ratio transformation, where a multivariate normal noise term is added to the log odds, in other words (and equivalently):

$$\left(\log\left(\frac{\pi_{i1}}{\pi_{ij}}\right), \dots, \log\left(\frac{\pi_{i(J-1)}}{\pi_{ij}}\right)\right) \sim N_{J-1}$$

$$\pi_i = \text{alr}^{-1}(Z_i + \varepsilon_i)$$

$$\varepsilon_i \sim N_{J-1}(0, \Sigma)$$

2.1 Fixed-Effects MLN

The FMLN() function fits the purely fixed effects version of multinomial logistic-normal regression [5], where:

$$\pi_i = \text{alr}^{-1}(X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i)$$

The model is fit via a Gibbs sampler with Metropolis or Metropolis-Hastings (depending on proposal distribution) proposals for the latent $W_i = X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i$. The algorithm iteratively proceeds:

- (1) Sample all $W_i | Y_i, X_i, \beta, \Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{J-1}$ via Metropolis-Hastings (latent variables; depending on proposal distribution)
- (2) Sample $\beta | W, X, \Sigma \sim N$ (fixed effects)
- (3) Sample $\Sigma | W, X, \beta \sim \text{Inv-Wishart}$ (residual covariance)

2.2 Mixed-Effects MLN

To accommodate more complex data structures, including group level variation (for $m = 1, \dots, M$ groups), the MMLN() function introduces estimation of random intercepts, where:

$$\pi_{mi} = \text{alr}^{-1}(X_{mi}\beta + \psi_m + \varepsilon_{mi})$$

and

$$\psi_m \sim N_{J-1}(0, \Phi)$$

while the rest of the model parameterization remains the same. This mixed effects multinomial logistic-normal model [5] is fit via a Metropolis-within-Gibbs sampler extended from the one used to fit the fixed effects version:

- (1) Sample all $W_{mi} | Y_{mi}, X_{mi}, \beta, \psi_m, \Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{J-1}$ via Metropolis-Hastings (latent variables; depending on proposal distribution)
- (2) Sample $\psi_m | W, X, \beta, \Sigma, \Phi \sim N$ (random effects)
- (3) Sample $\Phi | \Psi \sim \text{Inv-Wishart}$ (random effects covariance; Ψ is the full matrix of random effects)
- (4) Sample $\beta | W, X, \Psi, \Sigma \sim N$ (fixed effects)
- (5) Sample $\Sigma | W, X, \beta \sim \text{Inv-Wishart}$ (residual covariance)

2.3 Mahalanobis Residuals

Recently, randomized quantile residuals for binary outcomes [3] were extended for use in nominal multinomial modeling frameworks [6]. These residuals take the form of squared Mahalanobis distances in the transformed additive log-ratio space from the observed data to the samples from a predictive distribution under any model fit. These residuals, implemented in the MDres() function, are not specific to any multinomial model. Generally, for each observation i , K samples of predicted counts y_{ik} are generated from a fitted multinomial model to form the sampling distribution of the additive log-ratio transformed vectors:

$$w_{ik} = \text{alr}(y_{ik}^*), k = 1, 2, \dots, K$$

Squared Mahalanobis distances of these model-generated log-odds, $\{w_i\}$, as well as for the observed log-odds, w_i^{obs} are calculated:

$$MD_{ik}^2 = ((w_{ik} - \bar{w}_i)^T \hat{\Sigma}_{w_i}^{-1} (w_{ik} - \bar{w}_i))$$

and

$$MD_i^{2(obs)} = ((w_i^{obs} - \bar{w}_i)^T \hat{\Sigma}_{w_i}^{-1} (w_i^{obs} - \bar{w}_i))$$

where \bar{w}_i is the sample mean of model-generated log-odds and $\hat{\Sigma}_{w_i}$ is their sample covariance matrix.

A percentile for the observed distance, $MD_i^{2(obs)}$ relative to the empirical cdf of the model-generated distances, $\hat{F}_K(MD_i^2)$ is calculated. A uniform random variable is then generated where the minimum, a_i , and maximum, b_i , depend on the observed value's ordered location among the model-based MD_i^2 :

- (1) If $MD_i^{2(obs)} \leq \min(MD_i^2)$

$$u_i \sim \mathcal{U}(a_i = 0, b_i = \hat{F}_K(\min(MD_i^2)))$$
- (2) If $MD_i^{2(obs)} > \max(MD_i^2)$

$$u_i \sim \mathcal{U}(a_i = \hat{F}_K(\max(MD_i^2)), b_i = 1)$$
- (3) Otherwise,

$$u_i \sim \mathcal{U}(a_i = \hat{F}_K(\tilde{MD}_i^2), b_i = \hat{F}_K(MD_i^{2(obs)}))$$

where $\tilde{MD}_i^2 = \max(MD_i^2 < MD_i^{2(obs)})$

If the data fit the model, these percentiles are distributed $\mathcal{U}(0,1)$. These percentiles are back-transformed to standard normal values to serve as residuals, $r_i = \Phi^{-1}(u_i)$. Normal quantile-quantile and residual plots are then used to assess fit.

3. The MMLN R Package

3.1 Package Structure

The package is organized into four main R scripts:

- **mln_helpers.R**: utility functions
- **mln_functions.R**: core MCMC samples FMLN() and MMLN()
- **multi_res**: Mahalanobis residuals MDres(), summary and plotting helpers
- **real_data_examples.R**: vignettes for applying the functions to real data sets

3.2 Function Overview

Table 1 gives the description for the three primary functions of the package, as well as the three most important helper functions. There are several other functions which are discussed as needed.

Table 1: Primary MMLN Package Functions

<i>Function</i>	<i>Description</i>
FMLN	Fit fixed-effects MLN model via MH-Gibbs sampling
MMLN	Fit mixed-effects MLN model with group-level random intercepts
plot_trace_and_summary	Generate traceplots and posterior summary tables
compute_dic	Calculate DIC from log-likelihood samples
sample_posterior_predictive	Simulate posterior predictive counts for model checking
MDres	Compute Mahalanobis residuals

3.3 Using FMLN

The FMLN() function takes as its primary arguments the count matrix Y and input matrix X of fixed-effects covariates. Parameters also include the total number of MCMC iterations, burn-in (number of initial iterations to discard), thinning interval, scaling factor for Metropolis-Hastings proposal covariance, settings for the prior distributions on the fixed effects and residual covariance matrix, and choice of proposal distribution for the Metropolis-Hastings. The verbose argument allows for printing of progress updates.

```
res_f <- FMLN (  
  Y           = sim$Y,  
  X           = sim$X,  
  n_iter      = 2000,  
  burn_in    = 500,  
  thin       = 2,  
  proposal   = "normbeta",  
  verbose    = TRUE  
)
```

3.4 Using MMLN

The MMLN() function behaves similarly to the FMLN(), though now requires the definition of the Z random effects design matrix, currently only supporting random intercepts for group-level observations. All other arguments remain the same, though the prior settings also now account for the inclusion of the random effects.

```
res_m <- MMLN (  
  Y           = sim$Y,  
  X           = sim$X,  
  Z           = sim$Z,  
  n_iter      = 2000,  
  burn_in    = 500,  
  thin       = 2,  
  proposal   = "normbeta",  
  verbose    = TRUE  
)
```

3.5 Diagnostic Tools

Trace plots and posterior Markov chain summaries can be displayed with the `plot_trace_and_summary()` function after passing one of the posterior chain objects returned by either `FMLN()` or `MMLN()` through the `simplify2array()` function. By default, the trace plots are displayed in groups of four.

```
beta_chain_array <- simplify2array(res_m$beta_chain)
trace_stats      <- plot_trace_and_summary(beta_chain_array,
"beta")
trace_stats
```

The Deviance Information Criterion (DIC) [2] for comparing model fits is computed via the `compute_dic()` function after using the returned posterior chains and the true data counts to estimate the log likelihood functions using the `dmnl_loglik()` function.

```
ll_chain <- sapply(res_m$w_chain,
                  function(W) dmnl_loglik(W, sim$Y))
W_hat   <- alr(compress_counts(sim$Y) / rowSums(sim$Y))
ll_hat  <- dmnl_loglik(W_hat, sim$Y)
dic_res <- compute_dic(ll_chain, ll_hat)
```

Finally, the squared Mahalanobis residuals can be computed for any set of predictive distribution samples for each observation using the `MDres()` function. The function has a `summary()` class method which prints out the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality as a formal test of model fit and displays the normal quantile-quantile plot of the residuals for a convenient graphical assessment.

```
Y_pred_list <- lapply(seq_along(res_m$w_chain), function(i) {
  sample_posterior_predictive(X      = sim$X,
                              beta   = res_m$beta_chain[[i]],
                              Sigma  = res_m$sigma_chain[[i]],
                              n      = sim$n,
                              Z      = sim$Z,
                              psi    = res_m$psi_chain[[i]],
                              mixed  = TRUE
  )
})
resids <- MDres(sim$Y, Y_pred_list)
summary(resids)
```

3.5.1 Example Output

The `MMLN` package also includes several vignettes for demonstrating the implementation and utility of the models and diagnostic output on both simulated and real data. One vignette involves helper function, `run_pollen_models()`, that shows the residuals ability to capture the well-established existence of overdispersion [7] in pollen count data. There is also a `simulate_mixed_mln_data()` function which will simulate data from the `MMLN` model. As an example, we simulate data under the `MMLN`, then fit those data with both the `MMLN()` and `FMLN()` functions. The example Figure 1, and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results presented demonstrate one use case of the Mahalanobis residuals and its summary class method.

Figure 1: Example QQ-plots of summary(MDres) output for FMLN (left) and MMLN (right) models fit to MMLN data.

```
> resid <- MDres(observed_counts, fitted_counts_list)
> summary(resid)
Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality of Mahalanobis residuals:
  Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

D = 0.13429, p-value = 0.05429
alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

4. Discussion and Future Work

The **MMLN** package equips users with flexible tools for modeling multinomial outcomes in the presence of overdispersion, together with comprehensive diagnostics via squared Mahalanobis residuals. The modular design and simple interfaces facilitate usage and application to a wide range of data. Future extensions are planned to include handling of more robust random effects, as the infrastructure of the mixed effects model should be easily extended:

$$W_{mi} = X_{mi}\beta + Z_{mi}\psi_m + \varepsilon_{mi}$$

$$\text{vec}(\psi_m) \sim N_{(J-1)q}(0, \Phi)$$

where, given q group-level random covariates, the log-odds latent variables have the multivariate normal distribution:

$$W_{mi}|X_{mi}, \beta, \psi_m, \Sigma \sim N_{(J-1)}(X_{mi}\beta + Z_{mi}\psi_m, \Sigma)$$

and, unconditionally:

$$\text{vec}(W_m)|X_{mi}, \beta, \Sigma \sim N_{(J-1)n_i}(\text{vec}(X_m\beta), Q_m^{-1})$$

where

$$Q_m^{-1} = (Z_m \otimes I_{(J-1)})\Phi(Z_m \otimes I_{(J-1)})^T + (I_{n_m} \otimes \Sigma)$$

However, the addition of additional random effects drastically increases computation cost, and will thus require more robust implementation, perhaps by leveraging the **Rcpp** package [4] for integrating R and C++. In the future, support for alternative priors for the parameters of the Bayesian model may also be included.

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